

Manuscript Number: COMNET-D-15-513

Title: ANDSF-Assisted Vertical Handover Decisions in the IEEE 802.11/LTE-Advanced Network

Article Type: Regular Paper

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ANDSF-Assisted Vertical Handover Decisions in the IEEE 802.11/LTE-Advanced Network

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1. INTRODUCTION

Existing cellular and wireless local area networks (WLANs) are undergoing unprecedented architectural and technical enhancements to their fundamental operation. IEEE has recently updated the baseline version of the IEEE 802.11 Standard for wireless local area access [1], providing technical corrections / clarifications to the baseline operation of the previous standard and incorporating various enhancements to existing medium access and physical layer functions. These include higher data rates, use of power control, and provision for advanced radio measurements. On the other hand, Release 10 of the 3GPP Long Term Evolution (LTE) system, a.k.a., LTE-Advanced (LTE-A), also provisions for exciting new enhancements to the LTE system, such as carrier aggregation, advanced multi-antenna techniques, relaying and enhanced support for heterogeneous networking [2].

The smooth integration of the 3GPP cellular systems and the IEEE-based WLANs has always been challenging [3]. Aiming to realize the so-called heterogeneous networking paradigm, 3GPP provided several functional enhancements to the Evolved Packet Core (EPC) of the LTE-A system, such as the deployment of the Access Network Discovery and Selection Function (ANDSF) [4]-[5]. The ANDSF can assist the multi-mode mobile terminals (MMTs), i.e. devices equipped with both 3GPP and non-3GPP radio interfaces, to discover and select an appropriate Point of Attachment (PoA) in the heterogeneous network, i.e. either a 3GPP cell or a WLAN Access Point (AP).

Even though 3GPP specifies the baseline functionality of the ANDSF, it also enables the operators to deploy their own (implementation-dependent) inter-system mobility policy. On the other hand, the use of this policy depends on the MMT implementation, given that both the RAT selection and the PoA association are performed at the MMT, i.e., Vertical Handover (VHO). The VHO decision plays a key role in the supported QoS and the power consumption at the MMT, given that different RATs use different radio capabilities and result in varying power consumption per interface state [6]. Current literature includes a noteworthy amount of algorithms for horizontal and vertical handover decision for heterogeneous networks [7]-[9]. However, only a few works utilize the ANDSF functionality for efficient network discovery and seamless mobility at the MMT. In addition, even though the utilization of standard LTE-A measurements for handover has been recently proposed in [10], the joint utilization of the enhanced radio measurement capabilities of the LTE-A and the IEEE 802.11-2012 systems is an unexplored research area.

In this work, we propose the A-assisted eneRgy-effiCient vertical Handover decisiON (ARCHON) algorithm for the heterogeneous IEEE 802.11-2012 / LTE-A network. The proposed algorithm enables a MMT to identify the network PoA that minimizes its average overall power consumption and guarantees a mean SINR target for its ongoing connections. ARCHON is based on a) a 3GPP and IEEE compatible methodology for estimating the average overall MMT power consumption on a per candidate PoA basis, b) an energy-efficient inter-system mobility policy that translates the estimation methodology at the ANDSF to simple energy-efficient decision thresholds for the MMT, and c) a novel intra-system mobility policy that allows the MMT to select the least power consuming PoA in the heterogeneous network.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents recent amendments in the 3GPP Long Term Evolution – Advanced (LTE-Advanced) and the IEEE 802.11-2012 (Wi-Fi)

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3 systems, focusing on the key measurement capabilities available at the mobile terminals and wireless
4 stations. In Section 3, we describe our system model and in section 4 we present the proposed
5 algorithm. A system-level simulation study is presented in Section 5 and our conclusions are drawn in
6 Section 6.
7

9 2. MEASUREMENT CAPABILITIES IN LTE-ADVANCED AND IEEE 802.11-2012

11 In this section, we summarize the most prominent measurement capabilities available at the wireless
12 PoAs and MMTs in the LTE-Advanced and IEEE 802.11-2012 systems. Accordingly, we present the
13 baseline functionality of the Access Network Discovery and Selection Function (ANDSF) module that
14 is part of the 3GPP system and is used to complement the VHO decision at the MMTs.
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18 A. IEEE 802.11-2012 Overview

20 IEEE 802.11 is a set of standards supporting wireless local area network (WLAN) access in the 2.4,
21 3.6 and 5 GHz frequency bands. The baseline version of the standard, i.e. IEEE 802.11-2007, has been
22 recently updated to its current version, i.e. IEEE 802.11-2012 [1], aiming to include a series of
23 amendments developed over the past few years, e.g. amendments 802.11k and 802.11n. The IEEE
24 802.11-2012 release includes technical corrections and clarifications to the baseline IEEE 802.11
25 standard, as well as enhancements to the existing medium access control (MAC) and physical layer
26 (PHY) functions, e.g. support for higher transmission/reception rates, use of power control, and radio
27 measurement capabilities.
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31 Let us now focus on the radio measurement capabilities in IEEE 802.11-2012, that were initially
32 developed under the IEEE 802.11k working group. The radio resource measurement (RRM) service
33 includes measurements that extend the capability, reliability, and maintainability of WLANs by
34 providing standard measurements across vendors. The measurement data are commuted to upper
35 layers of the communications stack. An IEEE 802.11-2012-conformant STA can make local
36 measurements, request a measurement from another STA, or be requested by another STA to make
37 one or more measurements and return the respective results. The radio measurement data is made
38 available to STA management and upper protocol layers, where it may be used for a wide range of
39 applications, such as radio resource and mobility management. Both the measurement requests and
40 reports are conveyed through IEEE 802.11 management frames, while they are as follows: beacon,
41 frame, channel load, noise histogram, STA Statistics, Location Configuration Information (LCI),
42 neighbor report, link measurement, and transmit stream/category measurement. A measurement pause
43 mechanism (request-only type mechanism) and a measurement pilot (report-only mechanism) are also
44 provisioned. Table II summarizes some of the basic STA measurement capabilities in IEEE 802.11-
45 2012, while it also includes the adopted notation for two tagged IEEE 802.11-2012-conformant STA
46 s, s' . Note that both the MMTs and PoAs are referred to as STAs according to [1]; thus the
47 measurement capabilities in Table II apply to both the MMT and the WLAN PoA sides.
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Measurement	Definition	Notation
Received Channel Power Indicator	An indication of the total channel power (signal, noise, and interference) of a received IEEE 802.11 frame, transmitted from STA s to STA s' , measured on the channel and at the antenna connector used to receive the frame at STA s' . The RCPI value can be translated in dBm according to the respective formula in [1].	$RCPI(s, s')$

(RCPI)		
Average Noise Power Indicator (ANPI)	A MAC indication of the average noise plus interference power measured by STA s , when the channel is idle as defined by three simultaneous conditions: 1) the Virtual CS mechanism indicates idle channel, 2) the STA s is not transmitting a frame, and 3) the STA s is not receiving a frame. The ANPI value can be translated in dBm according to the respective formula in [1].	$ANPI(s)$
Received Signal to Noise Indicator (RSNI)	An indication of the signal to noise plus interference ratio of a received IEEE 802.11 frame, transmitted from STA s to STA s' . RSNI is defined by the ratio of the received signal power (RCPI-ANPI) to the noise plus interference power (ANPI) as measured on the channel and at the antenna connector used to receive the frame.	$RSNI(s, s')$
Max Transmit Power (MTP)	The Max Transmit Power field is a 2's complement signed integer and is 1 octet in length, providing an upper limit, in units of dBm, on the transmit power as measured at the output of the antenna connector to be used by STA s on the current channel. The maximum tolerance for the value reported in Max Transmit Power field shall be 5 dB. The value of the Max Transmit Power field shall be less than or equal to the Max Regulatory Power value for the current channel.	$P_{max}(s)$
Transmit Power Used (TPU)	The Transmit Power Used field is a 2's complement signed integer and is 1 octet in length. It shall be less than or equal to the Max Transmit Power and indicates the actual power used as measured at the output of the antenna connector, in units of dBm, by STA s when transmitting the frame containing the Transmit Power Used field. The Transmit Power Used value is determined any time prior to sending the frame in which it is contained and has a tolerance of ± 5 dB.	$P_{used}(s)$

Table I: IEEE 802.11-2012 measurement capabilities [1]

B. LTE-Advanced overview

3GPP has recently provided the Release 9 series of standards for the LTE system [2], which provisions a peak cell data rate of 300Mbps and 75Mbps in the downlink and uplink directions, respectively, under various mobility and network deployment scenarios. A key difference from previous 3GPP standards is the incorporation of the Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) access and the Single Carrier Frequency Division Multiple Access (SC-FDMA) for the LTE downlink and uplink directions, respectively. Another important feature of the LTE system is the adoption of Adaptive Modulation and Coding (AMC) along with Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) transceivers, in both the LTE access network and the User Equipment (UE), which enable resourceful utilization of the LTE spectrum pool. The detailed network architecture along with the Mobility Management (MM) procedures for the LTE system can be found in [2].

To resourcefully facilitate the mobility and the radio resource management procedures, the Release 9 series of standards for the LTE system includes a wide set of signal quality measurements for both the LTE access network and UEs. Table I summarizes part of the measurements capabilities in the LTE access network and the LTE UEs [15], while it additionally includes notation for a tagged LTE UE $u \in \mathbf{U}$ and LTE cell $c \in \mathbf{C}$. Note that $R_{c,DL}$ and $R_{c,UL}$ correspond to the number of utilized Resource Blocks (RB) within the operating bandwidth of cell $c \in \mathbf{C}$. The LTE measurements presented in Table I will be utilized in the following section for the VHO decision phase.

Measurement	Definition	Performed by	Notation
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Reference signal received power (RSRP)	The linear average over the power contributions (in [W]) of the resource elements that carry cell-specific reference signals within the considered measurement frequency bandwidth. For RSRP determination the cell-specific reference signals R0 shall be used while if the UE may use R1 in addition to R0 if it is reliably detected. The reference point for the RSRP shall be the antenna connector of the UE.	UE	$RSRP(c)$
E-UTRA Carrier Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI)	The linear average of the total received power (in [W]) observed only in OFDM symbols containing reference symbols for antenna port 0, over $R_{c,DL}$ number of RBs by the UE from all sources, including co-channel serving and non-serving cells, adjacent channel interference, thermal noise etc. RSSI is not reported as a stand-alone measurement rather it is utilized for deriving RSRQ.	UE	$RSSI(c)$
Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ)	The ratio $R_{c,DL} \times RSRP / (E\text{-UTRA carrier RSSI})$ where $R_{c,DL}$ is the number of RB's of the E-UTRA carrier RSSI measurement bandwidth. The measurements in the numerator and denominator shall be made over the same set of RBs. The reference point for the RSRQ shall be the antenna connector of the UE.	UE	$RSRQ(c)$
Downlink Reference Signal Transmitted Power (DL RS Tx)	The linear average over the power contributions (in [W]) of the resource elements that carry cell-specific reference signals which are transmitted by a tagged cell within its operating system bandwidth. For DL RS TX power determination the cell-specific reference signals R0 and if available R1 can be used. The reference point for the DL RS TX power measurement shall be the TX antenna connector.	E-UTRAN	$P_{RS}(c)$
Received Interference Power	The uplink received interference power, including thermal noise, within one physical RB's bandwidth of N_{sc}^{RB} resource elements. The reported value shall contain a set of Received Interference Powers for all the uplink physical RBs. The reference point for the measurement shall be the RX antenna connector.	E-UTRAN	$I(c)$

Table II: LTE UE and network measurements [15]

C. 3GPP ANDSF overview

The release 9 series of standards for the LTE system provisions access to non-3GPP systems, including IEEE 802.16x series of standards for Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX) and the IEEE 802.11x series of standards for WLAN access (Wi-Fi), towards facilitating heterogeneous network utilization at the MMTs. The substantially increased number of PoAs of heterogeneous RATs, however, necessitates more sophisticated network discovery and selection procedures. To this end, 3GPP provisioned the deployment of the Access Network Discovery and Selection Function (ANDSF) module, which contains data management and control functionality necessary to provide access network discovery and selection assistance data as per operators' policy. The ANDSF responds to UE requests for access network discovery information (pull mode), while it is able to initiate data transfer to the UE (push mode) based on network triggers or as a result of previous communication with the UE. Three types of information are provided by the ANDSF: the inter-system mobility policy, the access network discovery information and the inter-system routing policy.

The inter-system mobility policy is a set of operator-defined rules and preferences that affect the inter-system mobility decisions taken by the UE. The UE uses the inter-system mobility policy when it can route IP traffic only over a single radio access interface, at a given time, in order to a) decide when

inter-system mobility is allowed or restricted, and b) to select the most preferable access technology type or access network that should be used to access the EPC. The access network discovery information may include the access technology type (e.g. WLAN, WiMAX), the radio access network identifier (e.g. the SSID of a WLAN), other technology specific information, e.g. one or more carrier frequencies, as well as validity conditions, i.e. conditions indicating when the provided access network discovery information is valid (e.g. a location). The UE may retain and use the access network discovery information provided by the ANDSF until new/updated information is retrieved. Finally, the Inter-System Routing Policy is utilized to route IP traffic simultaneously over multiple radio access interfaces i.e., simultaneous utilization of different RANs. This information is utilized for deciding whether a RAN is restricted for a specific IP traffic flow and in general, for selecting the most preferable RANs to route IP traffic that matches specific criteria (e.g. all traffic to a specific PoA, or all traffic belonging to a specific IP flow, or all traffic of a specific application, etc). The roaming architecture for the ANDSF module is depicted in Figure 1, where H-ANDSF stands for the Home-ANDSF module and V-ANDSF for the Visiting-ANDSF module while on UE roaming. Note that the ANDSF services are provided to the UE via the S14 interface [2]. A more detailed analysis regarding the ANDSF functionality can be found in [4][5].

Figure 1: Roaming Architecture for Access Network Discovery Support Functions

Even though the deployment of the ANDSF module is optional [9], current literature identifies the ANDSF as an important enabler for efficient VHO decision making at the MMT side [3][6][10]. In this work, the ANDSF module is assumed to communicate with the PoAs within the HWN, both with LTE and WLAN PoA, in order to acquire standardized network measurements regarding their current status. These measurements, included in Table I and II, are utilized by the ANDSF module to facilitate the VHO procedure at the MMTs by forming a novel power consumption minimization inter-system mobility policy on a per MMT basis. This policy is subsequently commuted to the MMT through the S14 interface, on demand, which utilizes it to decide on a VHO according to the proposed VHO decision algorithm. The procedure above enables the utilization of the VHO decision making phase as a powerful tool for reducing the overall power consumption at the MMT side, without compromising the provided QoS.

3. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a heterogeneous wireless network (HWN), consisted of a) a set of 3GPP LTE PoAs \mathcal{C} , b) a set of IEEE 802.11k-conformant WLAN PoAs \mathcal{W} , and c) a set of Multi-mode Mobile Terminals (MMTs) \mathcal{U} equipped with both LTE and IEEE 802.11-2012-conformant radio access interfaces (Fig. 2). The ANDSF module is assumed to facilitate the VHO decision at the MMTs, by providing a) an appropriate candidate PoA set (network discovery information), and b) an inter-system mobility policy with respect to the candidate PoA set (described in the following), through the standardized S14 interface. Each PoA within the HWN is assumed to perform standardized network measurements and convey them to the ANDSF as described in the following. Even though the detailed procedure according to which the ANDSF module decides on the most suitable candidate PoA set for each MMT is out of the scope of this work, the procedure for acquiring the network measurements for a tagged candidate PoA will be described in detail in the following.

Fig. 2: Heterogeneous Wireless Network

Depending on the particular characteristics of the ongoing user service, each MMT $u \in \mathcal{U}$ is assumed to have a mean SINR target γ_l and bandwidth requirement B_{LTE} on service reception from the LTE network, and a mean SINR target γ_w and bandwidth requirement B_{WLAN} on service reception from the WLAN network. Note that different mean SINR target and bandwidth requirements are allowed for the two systems, owing to their heterogeneous communication characteristics, e.g. incorporation of MIMO and allowed AMC schemes. In the following, it is also assumed that an active radio access interface of a tagged MMT i.e., an interface which is switched-on and connected to a PoA, can be in one of the communication states in $\mathcal{S} := \{T, R, I\}$, where T corresponds to the transmit, R to the receive, and I to the idle states, respectively.

A. Power Consumption Model

Let us now focus on the power consumption model of an active MMT $u \in \mathbf{U}$. For a tagged time interval TTT the expected power consumption of the LTE interface is given as follows:

$$P_{LTE} = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} p_{LTE}(s) \cdot P_{LTE}(s) \quad (1)$$

, where $P_{LTE}(s)$ corresponds to the average power consumption in state $s \in \mathcal{S}$ for the LTE interface and $p_{LTE}(s)$ to the probability of the LTE interface being in state $s \in \mathcal{S}$, both of which are measured within the decision time interval TTT . Following a similar approach and notation, the expected power consumption corresponding to the WLAN interface is given as follows:

$$P_{WLAN} = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} p_{WLAN}(s) \cdot P_{WLAN}(s) \quad (2)$$

In (1) and (2), the parameters $p_{LTE}(s)$ and $p_{WLAN}(s)$ depend on the particular characteristics of the ongoing user service, while they can also vary with respect to the channel state and the RAT type of the target PoA, e.g. a bad channel increases the probability of retransmissions which, in turn, alters the sojourn time per interface state. These probabilities can be derived either through theoretical analysis, e.g. [11] includes some references for VoIP modeling with Markov chains, or through simulation and analysis, or by utilizing PHY or MAC interface monitoring techniques. In this work, these probabilities are assumed to be known and fixed (but not equal) for both RATs.

Let us now focus on the power consumption parameters per interface state and RAT type. Current literature includes numerous reports for estimating the power consumption values per interface state with respect to the RAT type of the MMT interface [6] [12] [13]. However, in [6] it is shown that the power consumption at the MMT side is highly correlated to a plethora of statically and dynamically changing parameters such as supported standard, distance between the MMT and the target PoA, interface manufacturer, underlying computer engine, adopted interface state set, current channel state, and current traffic pattern characteristics. Even though the power consumption at the receive and idle state can be assumed fixed, the power consumption at the transmit state is closely related to the mean SINR target, the interference and noise at the PoA site, as well as the channel gain between the MMT and the target PoA. In this work, even though the power consumption on the receive and idle interface states are assumed fixed and known, the power consumption for the transmit state is allowed to vary with respect the MMT and the target PoA status, for both the LTE and the WLAN interfaces.

Following a similar approach with [13], the power consumption on the transmit interface state is decomposed to a) the base power consumption of the radio access interface and b) the transmitted power of the interface. As a result, for a tagged time interval T and MMT $u \in \mathbf{U}$, the expected power consumption on the LTE and WLAN transmit state is given as in (3) and (4), respectively, where $P_{B,LTE}$ and $P_{B,WLAN}$ corresponds to the base power consumption of the LTE and WLAN radio access interfaces while $P_{t,LTE}$ and $P_{t,WLAN}$ to the respective transmitted power per interface.

$$P_{LTE}(T) = P_{B,LTE} + P_{t,LTE} \quad (3)$$

$$P_{WLAN}(T) = P_{B,WLAN} + P_{t,WLAN} \quad (4)$$

The following analysis is pursued to express the transmitted power per RAT type with respect to signal quality measurements which can be estimated based on MMT or network measurements. For a tagged LTE PoA $c \in \mathcal{C}$, MMT $u \in \mathcal{U}$ and time interval TTT , the expected mean SINR in the LTE uplink direction i.e, the mean SINR as seen by the LTE PoA c within the time interval TTT , is given as follows:

$$\gamma_{LTE}(c) = \frac{P_{t,LTE}(c) \cdot h_{LTE}(u,c)}{(I_{LTE}(c) + (\sigma_{LTE}(c))^2)} \quad (5)$$

, where $P_{t,LTE}(c)$ corresponds to the average transmitted power at the MMT for the LTE interface, $h_{LTE}(u,c)$ to the average channel gain from MMT u to the LTE PoA c , $I_{LTE}(c)$ to the average interference power at the LTE PoA c , and $(\sigma_{LTE}(c))^2$ to the average noise power at the LTE PoA c , all averaged within the time interval TTT . Using (7) and taking into account the mean SINR target $\bar{\gamma}_{LTE}$ for sustaining the MMT services, it can be readily shown that the expected power transmission of MMT u within the time interval TTT is given as follows:

$$P_{t,LTE}(c) = \frac{\bar{\gamma}_{LTE} \cdot (I_{LTE}(c) + (\sigma_{LTE}(c))^2)}{h_{LTE}(u,c)} \quad (6)$$

Following a similar approach for a tagged WLAN PoA $w \in \mathcal{W}$, it can be shown that the expected power transmission of MMT u within the time interval T is given as follows:

$$P_{t,WLAN}(w) = \frac{\bar{\gamma}_{WLAN} \cdot (I_{WLAN}(w) + (\sigma_{WLAN}(w))^2)}{h_{WLAN}(u,w)} \quad (7)$$

, where $I_{WLAN}(w)$ corresponds to the average interference power at the WLAN PoA w , $(\sigma_{WLAN}(w))^2$ to the average noise power at the WLAN PoA w , and $h_{WLAN}(u,w)$ to the channel gain from the MMT u to the WLAN PoA w , all averaged within the time interval TTT .

By carefully examining (6) and (7) it can be seen that the transmitted power per interface, can be estimated with respect to a) the mean SINR target which is known to the MMT, b) the received interference and noise power at the PoA site, and c) the channel gain between the MMT and the PoA set. In the sequel, we present a novel MMT power consumption minimization inter-system mobility policy that is based on standardized LTE and WLAN measurements commuted to the ANDSF. This policy is conveyed to the MMT through the standard 3GPP S14 interface, which subsequently utilizes it to perform a VHO (if needed).

4. THE PROPOSED VHO DECISION ALGORITHM

This section describes a backwards-compatible methodology for estimating the average overall MMT power consumption (section 4.1), presents two novel inter-system and intra-system mobility policies for the heterogeneous WLAN / LTE-A network (Sections 4.2 and 4.3, respectively), and provides the ARCHON algorithm (Section 4.4).

4.1 Power Consumption Estimation

Let \mathbf{U}_c denote the set of all interfering LTE-A users operating in the same frequency band with cell c . The mean uplink SINR between user u and cell c is given as follows:

$$\gamma(c) = \frac{t(u) \cdot h(u,c)}{\sum_{u' \in \mathbf{U}_c} t(u') \cdot h(u',c) + \sigma(c)^2} \quad (4)$$

where the numerator corresponds to the signal strength from user u in cell c and the denominator to the interference caused by all interfering users plus the noise power in cell c . Given the prescribed mean SINR target γ_l , the mean transmit power of user u in cell c can be computed as in Eq. (5).

$$t(u) = \frac{\gamma_l \cdot (\sum_{u' \in \mathbf{U}_c} t(u') \cdot h(u',c) + \sigma(c)^2)}{h(u,c)} \quad (5)$$

Following a similar approach with [10], it can be shown that the mean transmit power in Eq. (5) can be estimated based on standard LTE-A measurements as follows:

$$t(u) = \gamma_l \cdot \frac{T_{RS}(c)}{RSRP(c)} \cdot I(c) \quad (6)$$

where the ratio $\frac{P_{RS}(c)}{RSRP(c)}$ is used to assess the multiplicative inverse of the path loss between user u and cell c [10], i.e., the ratio $\frac{1}{h(u,c)}$. Note that all measurements in Eq. (6) are assumed to be averaged within the operating bandwidth of the target cell over the time interval Time to Trigger (TTT).

Under the same viewpoint, the expected transmit power of user u in a target WLAN AP can be also estimated by using standard WLAN measurements as follows:

$$t(w) = \gamma_w \cdot \frac{T_{TPU}(w)}{(RCPI(w) - ANPI(u))} \cdot ANPI(w) \quad (7)$$

where the ratio $\frac{T_{TPU}(w)}{(RCPI(w) - ANPI(w))}$ is used to estimate the multiplicative inverse of the path loss between user u and AP w . In the denominator of Eq. (7) we subtract the $ANPI(w)$ value from the $RCPI(w)$ provided that, by definition, the $RCPI(w)$ measurement includes the received signal power from all nearby cells [1] (including the serving cell). By combining Eq. (6) with Eq. (2) and Eq. (7) with Eq. (3), we can readily estimate the average overall power consumption for the LTE-A and WLAN interfaces, respectively, based on standard measurements and fixed parameters (Section II).

4.2 Energy-Efficient Inter-System Mobility Policy

The inter-system mobility policy, provided by the ANDSF, is used at the MMT to decide which of the available RATs to utilize. The inter-system mobility policy is provided in terms of rules, which are applicable under certain validity conditions [3][4]. In this section, we present an energy-efficient inter-system mobility policy for minimizing the average overall MMT power consumption. The proposed policy is built in the ANDSF based on a) fixed parameters, i.e., power consumption per state, probability of being in each interface state and mean SINR targets of the user, and b) standard LTE-A and WLAN measurements provided by the heterogeneous PoAs. The resulting set of rules is

subsequently commuted to the MMT to select the least power consuming available RAT. The inter-system mobility decision in the heterogeneous WLAN / LTE-A network can be broken down into two scenarios: the MMT is connected to the LTE-A system and decides whether it should switch to the WLAN interface, and vice versa.

Let us now focus on the first scenario, where a tagged MMT $u \in \mathbf{U}$ receives service from the LTE-A cell $c \in \mathbf{C}$. Let $\mathbf{L}_w \subseteq \mathbf{W}$ denote the candidate set of WLAN PoAs provided by the ANDSF. Then, the utilization of the WLAN interface is more preferable in terms of average overall MMT power consumption if the following condition is satisfied:

$$P_{WLAN}(w) < P_{LTE-A}(c), \text{ for at least one } w \in \mathbf{L}_w \quad (8)$$

where the notation $P_{WLAN}(w)$ corresponds to the average overall power consumption on service reception from the AP w . By substituting Eqs. (2), (3), (6) and (7) in Eq. (8), we can readily show that Eq. (8) results in the following condition:

$$RCPI(w) - ANPI(u) > A(c, w) \text{ for at least one } w \in \mathbf{L}_w \quad (9)$$

where the decision threshold $A(u, c, w)$ is given in Eq. (10).

$$A(c, w) = \frac{q_w(T) \cdot \gamma_w \cdot T_{TPU}(w) \cdot ANPI(w)}{\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} q_l(s) \cdot P_l(s) + q_l(T) \cdot \gamma_l \cdot \frac{T_{RS}(c)}{RSRP(c)} \cdot I(c) - \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} q_w(s) \cdot P_w(s)} \quad (10)$$

Following a similar approach for the second scenario, where the tagged MMT receives service from the WLAN AP $w \in \mathbf{W}$, and letting $\mathbf{L}_c \subseteq \mathbf{C}$ denote the set of candidate LTE-A cells, provided by the ANDSF, we can show that the utilization of the LTE-A interface is more preferable in terms of average overall power consumption at the MMT, if the following condition is satisfied:

$$RSRP(c) > A(w, c), \text{ for at least one } c \in \mathbf{L}_c \quad (11)$$

where the decision threshold $A(w, c)$ is given in Eq. (12).

$$A(w, c) = \frac{q_l(T) \cdot \gamma_l \cdot T_{RS}(c) \cdot I(c)}{\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} q_w(s) \cdot P_w(s) + q_w(T) \cdot \gamma_w \cdot \frac{T_{TPU}(w)}{RCPI(w) - ANPI(w)} \cdot ANPI(w) - \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} q_l(s) \cdot P_l(s)} \quad (12)$$

Note that the parameters in Eqs. (10) and (12) include a) standard LTE-A and WLAN PoA measurements, i.e., $T_{RS}(c)$, $I(c)$, $T_{TPU}(w)$ and $ANPI(w)$, which can be commuted to the ANDSF by using existing network signaling procedures, b) fixed and known values for the characteristics of the user's services, i.e., $q_l(s)$, $q_w(s)$, and SINR target, i.e., γ_l and γ_w , which can be provided by the serving PoA, and c) fixed and known values for the MMT power consumption per state, i.e., $P_l(s)$ and $P_w(s)$, which can be stored at the MMT and commuted to the ANDSF by using the push mode [4]-[5]. On the other hand, the left sides of Eqs. (9) and (11) include standard MMT measurements, i.e., $RSRP(c)$, $RCPI(w)$ and $ANPI(u)$, which can be performed locally at the MMT and readily utilized for VHO decision. Based on the aforementioned observation, we propose the following energy-efficient inter-system mobility policy:

Energy-Efficient Inter-System Mobility Policy

Rule 1: (LTE-A to IEEE 802.11-2012)

if the serving PoA is of LTE-A type

if $RCPI(w) - ANPI(u) > A(c, w)$ for at least one $w \in L_w$

 Switch on the IEEE 802.11-2012 interface

 Associate with $w \in L_w$

 Switch off the LTE-A interface

endif

endif

Rule 2: (IEEE 802.11-2012 to LTE-A)

if the serving PoA is of IEEE 802.11-2012 type

if $RSRP(c) > A(w, c)$ for at least one $c \in L_c$

 Switch-on the LTE-A interface

 Associate with $c \in L_c$

 Switch-off the IEEE 802.11-2012 interface

endif

endif

The proposed policy can be deployed in a backwards-compatible manner at the MMT by conducting standard measurements locally and by acquiring the thresholds $A(c, w)$ and $A(w, c)$ on-demand to the ANDSF.

4.3 Energy-Efficient Intra-System Mobility Policy

Even though the selection of the least power consuming RAT can be based on the proposed policy in Section III.B, the selection of the least power consuming PoA of the same RAT type remains an open issue, i.e., intra-system mobility. In this section, we present an energy-efficient intra-system mobility policy which utilizes a) standard measurements performed locally at the MMT, and b) the decision thresholds in Eqs. (10) and (12), provided by the ANDSF. We identify two different intra-system mobility decision scenarios: the intra-LTE-A and the intra-WLAN decision scenarios.

Let us focus on the intra-LTE-A scenario, where the tagged MMT $u \in \mathbf{U}$ receives service from the LTE-A cell $s \in \mathbf{C}$ and investigates the possibility of handing over to a LTE-A cell in the candidate set L_c , provided by the ANDSF. A handover from cell $s \in \mathbf{C}$ to a cell $c \in L_c$ will reduce the average overall MMT power if the following condition applies:

$$P_{LTE-A}(c) < P_{LTE-A}(s) \quad (13)$$

By using Eqs. (2) and (6), it can be shown that the condition in Eq. (13) is equivalent with the one in Eq. (14).

$$RSRP(c) > RSRP(s) \cdot \frac{T_{RS}(c) \cdot I(c)}{T_{RS}(s) \cdot I(s)} \quad (14)$$

1
2
3 Taking into account that the ratio $\frac{T_{RS}(c) \cdot I(c)}{T_{RS}(s) \cdot I(s)}$ is equal to $\frac{A(w,c)}{A(w,s)}$ (the denominators in the decision
4 thresholds are equal) and by extending Eq. (14) to the multi-cell decision scenario, we can readily
5 show that the selection of the least power consuming LTE-A cell can be based on the following
6 criterion:
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8

$$9 \quad \arg \max_{c \in L_c} RSRP(c) := \left\{ c \mid RSRP(c) > RSRP(s) \cdot \frac{A(w,c)}{A(w,s)} \right\} \quad (15)$$

10
11
12 where the decision thresholds $A(w, c)$ and $A(w, s)$ are taken with respect to a random WLAN PoA
13 $w \in L_w$.
14

15
16 Following a similar approach for the intra-WLAN scenario and letting v denote the serving WLAN
17 AP, we can readily show that the selection of the least power consuming AP can be based on the
18 following criterion:
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20

$$21 \quad \arg \max_{w \in L_w} (RCPI(w) - ANPI(w)) := \left\{ w \mid (RCPI(w) - ANPI(w)) > (RCPI(v) - ANPI(v)) \cdot \frac{A(c,w)}{A(c,v)} \right\} \quad (16)$$

22
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24 Interestingly, the set of parameters that allow the MMT to deploy the proposed energy-efficient
25 inter-system mobility policy, also enable it to select the least power consuming PoA of the same RAT
26 (energy-efficient intra-system mobility).
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29 4.4 The Proposed VHO Decision Algorithm

30
31 In this section, we integrate the energy-efficient inter-system and intra-system mobility policies
32 presented in Sections 4.2 and 4.3, respectively, into a single ANDSF-assisted energy-efficient VHO
33 decision algorithm: the ARCHON algorithm. The ARCHON algorithm utilizes local MMT
34 measurements and ANDSF information to select the least power consuming PoA in the heterogeneous
35 network under all feasible VHO decision scenarios, i.e., WLAN to LTE-A, LTE-A to WLAN, intra-
36 LTE-A and intra-WLAN. Let s denote the serving PoA when the MMT is connected to the LTE-A
37 system, and v when it is connected to the WLAN system. Based on the VHO decision policy for MMT
38 power consumption minimization, described in section III.C, and the HO decision policy for intra-
39 system MMT power consumption minimization, described in section III.D, in this section we propose
40 an energy-efficient VHO decision algorithm for the integrated LTE – WLAN network. The proposed
41 algorithm utilizes ANDSF context, built on standard measurements provided by both LTE and WLAN
42 PoAs, which is commuted to the MMT by using standard ANDSF pull procedures. By using this
43 context, the proposed VHO decision algorithm enables the MMT to always choose the least power
44 consuming RAT interface and PoA. The proposed algorithm is illustrated in Fig. 3.
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53 Upon VHO decision triggering, the proposed algorithm investigates whether the current serving PoA
54 of the MMT is a LTE cell or a WLAN AP. In the former case, the proposed algorithm follows the
55 steps illustrated in the upper area of the flowchart, whereas in the latter case, it follows the steps in the
56 lower area of the flowchart.
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58

59 When the serving PoA is a LTE cell, it initiates an ANDSF request to acquire the $RCPI_{MPCM}(w, c)$
60 parameters for all the WLAN AP in proximity. In the following, the proposed algorithm checks
61 whether there exists a WLAN AP that satisfies Eq. (9) (least power consuming compared to the
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serving LTE cell) and Eq. (16) (least power consuming WLAN AP). If there exists such a WLAN AP, denoted by w , it subsequently checks whether there exists another LTE cell with lower power consumption requirements. If it does, a HO request is initiated to the current serving LTE cell, while if it doesn't, a VHO procedure is performed towards the least power consuming WLAN AP w . In the scenario where the current LTE serving cell results in lower power consumption compared to any of the WLAN APs in proximity (upper right case), the proposed algorithm initiates an ANDSF request to acquire the parameters in Eq. (15), aiming to identify LTE cells that reduce the MMT power consumption. If such a cell exists, a HO request is sent to the current serving LTE cell, whereas in the opposite case, no action is taken and the VHO algorithm is terminated.

Figure 3: Proposed VHO decision algorithm

Let us now focus on the scenario where the current serving PoA is a WLAN AP (lower area in the flowchart). Following a similar approach, the VHO algorithm initiates an ANDSF request to acquire the $RSRP_{LTE}(c, w)$ parameters for all the LTE cells in proximity. In the following, the proposed algorithm checks whether there exists a LTE cell that satisfies Eq. (11) (least power consuming compared to the serving WLAN AP) and Eq. (15) (least power consuming LTE cell). If there exists such a LTE cell, denoted by c , it subsequently checks whether there exists another WLAN AP with lower power consumption requirements. If it does, the MMT initiates a HO towards the least power consuming WLAN AP w , while if it doesn't, a VHO procedure is performed towards the least power consuming LTE cell c . In the scenario where the current serving WLAN AP results in lower power consumption compared to any of the LTE cells in proximity (lower right case), the proposed algorithm initiates an ANDSF request to acquire the parameters in Eq. (16), aiming to identify WLAN APs that reduce the MMT power consumption. If such a WLAN AP exists, a HO request is sent to the current serving WLAN AP, whereas in the opposite case, no action is taken and the VHO algorithm is terminated.

4.5 Signaling Considerations

To deploy the proposed VHO decision algorithm, the ANDSF module should acquire the LTE and WLAN network measurements and parameters in (9), (11), (15), (16), for each member of the candidate PoA list. For a candidate PoA of WLAN RAT type $w \in \mathbf{W}$ this information includes a) the SSID of the WLAN PoA, b) the operating band, and c) the standard IEEE 802.11-2012 measurements in Table I. On the other hand, for a candidate PoA of LTE RAT type $c \in \mathbf{C}$ this information includes a) the E-UTRAN Cell Global Identifier, b) the operating channel, and c) the standard LTE measurements in Table II. This information will be referred to as VHO context in the following, for both the LTE and the WLAN systems.

Two different signaling procedures are identified to convey the required VHO context to the ANDSF module, i.e., the reactive and the proactive. In the reactive approach, the ANDSF module initiates a VHO context request towards the PoA of interest, i.e. a PoA included in the candidate PoA list for an active MMT, only upon a Network Discovery request by the active MMT. In the proactive approach, the required VHO context is derived on a periodic basis via establishing a connection between the ANDSF module and the PoA of interest. Even though this approach necessitates VHO context maintenance and increased network signaling, it may substantially reduce the VHO context derivation and VHO execution delay. The periodicity with which the VHO context should be reported is left as future work.

Fig. 4 and 5 provide an illustrative example of the required signaling for the reactive and the proactive VHO context derivation procedures, respectively, assuming that the UE has an active connection with LTE (eNB). Note that the signaling procedure depicted in Fig.2 and 3, does not correspond to the overall VHO execution signaling. Steps 9-12 are common for both approaches. Having obtained the candidate PoA list and the inter-system mobility policy, in step 9 the MMT decides on a) whether an inactive radio access interface should be switched on for performing link-quality measurements, and b) which PoAs in the list should be searched / measured. Steps 10 and 11 correspond to the measurement derivation phase for the LTE and the WLAN systems, respectively,

while in step 12 the VHO decision phase is employed. In more detail, given the candidate PoA set along with the MPCM inter-system mobility policy, both derived by the ANDSF, the MMT decides on whether a VHO should be executed.

Fig. 4: ANDSF signaling for the reactive VHO context derivation approach

Fig. 5: ANDSF signaling for the proactive VHO context derivation approach

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section includes extensive system-level simulation results to demonstrate the performance of the proposed MM approach. Section 5.1 summarizes the adopted simulation model and parameters, section 5.2 presents selected numerical results, whereas section 5.3 provides some take away results.

5.1 System-level simulation model and parameters

A conventional hexagonal LTE network is considered, including a main LTE cluster composed of 7 LTE cells, where each LTE cell consists of 3 hexagonal sectors. The wrap-around technique is used to extend the LTE network, by copying the main LTE cluster symmetrically on each of the 6 sides. A set of blocks of apartments, referred to as *WLANblocks*, are uniformly dropped within the main LTE cluster according to a scenario-related parameter d_{WB} indicating the WLAN block deployment density within the main LTE cluster. The WLAN blocks are modeled in accordance with the dual stripe model for dense urban environments shown in Fig. 6 [16]. According to it, each WLAN block consists of two stripes of apartments separated by a 10 m wide street while each stripe has two rows of $A = 5$ apartments of size 10×10 m. The WLAN APs are deployed with respect to a WLAN deployment ratio parameter $r_{wc} = 0.2$, indicating the probability of deploying a WLAN inside an apartment. Each WLAN AP is initially considered to provide service to one associated user. Both the WLAN APs and the associated users are uniformly dropped inside the apartment. Ten macrocell users are uniformly distributed within each LTE sector, while both the WLAN APs and the LTE users may freely move within the LTE cluster area in accordance with the mobility model summarized in Table I. Unless

differently stated, the user mobility model is characterized by an average user speed $\bar{v} = 3$ km/h and a standard speed deviation $s_u = 1$ km/h.

Figure 6: Dual-stripe WLAN block model for dense urban environments

The LTE cells utilize a 10MHz bandwidth and operate in one of the bands centered in 1990, 2000, and 2010 MHz. The LTE cell inter-site distance is set to 500m, while the WLAN APs are assumed to utilize one of the 1, 6, 11, and 14 ISM bands. The adopted Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS) are in accordance with [17] for both systems, while the Exponential Effective SINR Mapping method is used to obtain the effective SINR per RB and the consequential MMT throughput [16]. The minimum required SINR per MMT is set to $\bar{\gamma}_t = 2.88$ dB for both systems, while the communications are carried out in full buffer in accordance to the traffic model parameters shown in Table III. The shadowing standard deviation for the LTE and the WLAN systems are both assumed 8 dB, and the LTE and WLAN noise figures are set to 5 and 8 dB in that order. The LTE downlink RS power transmissions are normally distributed with a mean value of 23 dBm and a standard deviation of 3dB, whereas the respective WLAN beacon transmissions are normally distributed with a mean value of 23 dBm and a standard deviation of 3dB. The power class of the LTE radio access interface is set to 23dBm, while the power class for the WLAN interface is set to 20 dBm. The maximum transmission powers for the LTE and WLAN PoAs are set to 43 and 23dBm, respectively. The remainder simulations parameters, along with the aforementioned ones, are summarized in Table III, while Fig. 7 demonstrates a random snapshot for the network topology used in our system-level simulator. Note that the power consumption values for the LTE and WLAN interfaces are taken from [11] and [12], respectively.

Table III: System-level simulation parameters

Network layout	
Macrocell layout	7 clusters, 7 sites per cluster, 3 sectors per site, freq. reuse 1
Macrocell inter-site distance	500 m
Initial number of UEs per macrocell sector	10 UEs
Macrocell UE distribution	Uniform within each sector
WLAN block layout	Dual stripe model for dense urban environments [16]
WLAN block distribution in the main LTE cluster	Uniform
WLAN AP and UE distribution within an apartment	Uniform
Initial number of UEs per WLAN AP	1 UE

System operating parameters			
Parameter	Macrocell	WLAN	
Carrier frequency	Uniformly picked from the set { 1990, 2000, 2010 } MHz	Uniformly picked from the set { 2412, 2437, 2462, 2484 } MHz (bands 1,6, 11,14)	
Channel bandwidth	10 MHz	22 MHz	
Maximum Tx Power	46 dBm	20 dBm	
Antenna gain	14 dBi	5 dBi	
Noise figure	5 dB	8 dB	
Shadowing standard deviation	8 dB	8 dB	
Transmit power on the pilot signals	Normally distributed with a mean value of 23 dBm and standard deviation 3dB	Normally distributed with a mean value of 20 dBm and standard deviation 5dB	
Maximum Number of Users	50	20	
Link-to-system mapping	Effective SINR mapping (ESM) [16]		
Path Loss Models			
Path loss	Models for urban deployment in [16]		
Interior / Exterior wall penetration loss (indoor UEs)	5 / 15 dB		
UE parameters			
UE power class	LTE: 23 dBm, WLAN: 20 dBm		
UE antenna gain	LTE: 0 dBi, WLAN: 0 dBi		
Mean UL SINR target	LTE: $\gamma_t^{LTE} = 2.88$ dB, WLAN: $\gamma_t^{WLAN} = 2.88$ dB		
Traffic model WLAN	Full buffer similar to [16], $p_{WLAN}(T) = 0.4, p_{WLAN}(I) = 0.3,$ and $p_{WLAN}(R) = 0.3$		
Traffic model LTE	Full buffer similar to [16], $p_{LTE}(T) = 0.4, p_{LTE}(I) = 0.3,$ and $p_{LTE}(R) = 0.3$		
Power Consumption parameters WLAN	$P_{B,WLAN} = 924$ mW, $P_{WLAN}(R) = 594$ mW, $P_{WLAN}(I) = 80$ mW		
Power Consumption parameters LTE	$P_{B,LTE} = 1550$ mW, $P_{LTE}(R) = 1420$ mW, $P_{LTE}(I) = 160$ mW		
Mobility model [13]	User speed	$v_t = N(\bar{v}, s_u)$ m/s	
		Mean user speed	$\bar{v} = 3$ km/h
		User speed standard deviation	$s_u = 1$ km/h
	User direction	$\varphi_t = N\left(\varphi_{t-1}, 2\pi - \varphi_{t-1} \tan\left(\frac{\sqrt{v_t}}{2}\right)\Delta t\right)$ where Δt is the time period between two updates of the model, and $N(a, b)$ the Gaussian distribution of mean a and standard deviation b	
Other simulation parameters			
Overall simulation time	200 sec		
Simulation time unit	$\Delta t = 1$ sec		

The proposed algorithm is compared against a VHO algorithm that always prioritizes WLAN over LTE-A access, referred to as the baseline WLAN algorithm, and a VHO algorithm that always prioritizes LTE-A over WLAN access, referred to as the baseline LTE-A algorithm. The performance of all algorithms is averaged over both the LTE-A and WLAN systems/interfaces while it is plotted for

increasing d_{WB} . Unless differently stated, the performance of the algorithms is averaged over both the LTE and WLAN interfaces or PoAs.

5.2 System-level simulation results

Figure 7: Number of Users versus the WLANblock deployment density

Fig. 7 demonstrates the average number of users per RAT type for all algorithms and increasing WLANblock deployment density d_{WB} . Note that the total number of users in the system (black line) increases linearly for increasing WLANblock deployment density d_{WB} , provided that the introduction of additional WLANblocks not only increases the WLAN AP deployment density but also the number of users in the system (one additional user is introduced for each additional WLAN AP). As expected, all users are served by the LTE system for the baseline LTE VHO algorithm (dotted green line) until the maximum LTE capacity on the cells is reached, i.e., for $d_{WB} = 0.6$ the number of users is close to 350, where the remainder users are required to connect to the WLAN system (compact green line). In contrast, the number of WLAN users increases rapidly for the baseline WLAN VHO algorithm (dotted blue line) as the density of WLANblocks increases in the system, until all users are finally served by the WLAN system. Interestingly, the proposed algorithm is capable of balancing the number of users between the LTE and WLAN systems. However, this is achieved without sacrificing the energy saving opportunities provided by the WLAN system which, in the average, is more energy-efficient compared to the LTE one. As seen in Fig. 7, the proposed VHO algorithm sustains a roughly fixed number of LTE users which, in particular, are in such a range from the LTE macrocells that can result in lower power consumption compared to the one provided of the WLAN system. Summarizing, the proposed algorithm is capable of balancing the user load between the two heterogeneous systems, while attaining the lower power consumption for the MMTs (Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Mean MMT Power Consumption versus the WLANblock deployment density

Fig. 8 demonstrates the mean MMT power consumption for all algorithms and for increasing WLANblock deployment density within the main LTE cluster. As expected, prioritized access to the LTE system results in higher power consumption for the MMTs compared to both the baseline WLAN and proposed VHO decision algorithms. On the other hand, utilizing the WLAN infrastructure is shown to reduce the MMT power consumption compared to the baseline LTE algorithm, mainly owing to the shorter range nature of communications. The proposed algorithm is shown to reduce the MMT power consumption by up to 95% compared to the prioritized LTE access scenario (baseline LTE algorithm), with the higher gains attained in medium to high WLAN deployment densities, i.e., close to $0.4 < d_{WB} < 0.7$. In addition, the proposed algorithm is shown to greatly reduce the power consumption of the MMTs compared to the prioritized WLAN based algorithm (baseline WLAN) as well, providing power consumption gains that vary between 17% and 85%. On the average, the proposed algorithm reduces the power consumption of the MMTs compared to the baseline LTE system by approximately 82%, whereas it also reduces the MMT power consumption compared to the baseline WLAN system by 73% compared to the baseline WLAN algorithm as well.

Figure 9: Mean MMT Energy Consumption per bit versus the WLANblock deployment density

The positive impact of the enhanced power consumption, attained by the proposed VHO algorithm, is also evident in terms of mean energy consumption per bit (joules/bit) (Fig. 9). As shown in Fig. 9, the proposed algorithm reduces the mean energy consumption per bit for the MMTs by up to 93% compared to the baseline LTE VHO algorithm and up to 82% compared to the baseline WLAN algorithm. Interestingly, the proposed VHO algorithm cuts down to half the mean MMT energy consumption per bit compared to the other two competing algorithms, even when the WLAN deployment density is relatively low, i.e., $d_{WB} = 0.1$.

Figure 10: Mean MMT Transmit Power versus the WLANblock deployment density

Fig. 10 demonstrates the mean MMT transmit power for all algorithms and increasing WLANblock deployment density. Fig. 10 reveals that the reduced power consumption of the proposed algorithm not only originates from taking into account the actual power consumption per interface state, for the various RATs, but it is also a direct outcome of the algorithm's capability to account for the expected mean transmit power of the MMTs on the target PoAs. Interestingly, even though the proposed algorithm balances the number of users between the two different systems (Fig. 7) it is capable of lowering the mean MMT transmit power compared to the baseline WLAN algorithm (Fig. 10). In more detail, even though prioritizing WLAN access is expected to greatly reduce the mean transmit power for the MMTs, owing to the shorter transmit-receive range, this is not true in practice where a high utilization of the unlicensed ISM bands (high spectrum reusability) takes place leading to increased interference in the WLAN AP sites. Compared to the baseline WLAN algorithm, the proposed VHO algorithm reduces the required transmit power for the MMTs almost twofold, owing to the fact that it accounts for the interference at the PoA sites as well as the actual channel gain between the user and the target PoA. The same implies for the comparison between the proposed and the baseline LTE algorithm.

Figure 11: Mean PoA Received Interference Power versus the WLANblock deployment density

As expected, the positive impact of the reduced MMT transmit power, attained by the proposed VHO algorithm, is also depicted in terms of mean received interference power at the PoA sites (Fig. 11). The baseline LTE algorithm is shown to result in the highest interference at the PoA sites, on the average, owing to the severe underutilization of the WLAN infrastructure (Fig. 7) which does not allow for the decongestion of the LTE system. Nevertheless, when the maximum user capacity is reached for the LTE system (Fig. 8 for $d_W > 0.6$), the WLAN infrastructure is utilized and the mean PoA interference is ultimately being reduced. Fig. 11 also shows that even though the proposed algorithm utilizes the LTE infrastructure, the mean received interference performance at the PoAs is similar or even improved compared to the baseline WLAN algorithm. More importantly, the proposed algorithm is shown to greatly reduce the interference at the WLAN APs

(dotted red line) in medium to high WLAN deployment densities, compared to the baseline WLAN algorithm (compact blue line), by up to 5 dBs, an improvement which is higher than a threefold decrease.

Figure 12: Mean Uplink Capacity per User versus the WLANblock deployment density

The smart utilization of both the LTE and WLAN systems, both in terms of balancing the number of users in the two systems (Fig. 7) and in terms of lowering the interference at the PoA sites (Fig. 11), enables the proposed VHO algorithm to attain a significantly increased mean uplink capacity for the MMTs as well, compared to both the baseline WLAN and the baseline LTE algorithms (Fig. 12). Note that the mean uplink capacity per user corresponds to the uplink capacity that a user can attain if it fully utilizes the available bandwidth to its serving cell without using a specific mean SINR threshold. As expected, the baseline WLAN algorithm attains an improved mean uplink capacity per user compared to the baseline LTE algorithm, which tends to attain a roughly fixed performance for $d_W > 0.5$. Note that the performance of the baseline LTE algorithm improves above this value, given that the utilization of the WLAN infrastructure increases (Fig. 7).

Figure 13: Mean PoA Transmit Power versus the WLANblock deployment density

Fig. 13 demonstrates the mean PoA transmit power for all algorithms and increasing WLANblock deployment density. As expected, the baseline LTE algorithm results in the highest transmit power at the PoA given that it is based on prioritizing the utilization of the macrocell infrastructure. On the other hand, the baseline WLAN algorithm is shown to result in the lower PoA transmit power owing to the highest possible utilization of the short-range nature of WLAN access. Referring to the performance of the proposed algorithm, three key observations are important to note. At first, the proposed algorithm requires increased PoA transmit power on the average (compact red line) compared to the baseline WLAN (compact blue line), owing to the higher utilization of the LTE infrastructure. Nevertheless, if we focus on the WLAN infrastructure only, the proposed algorithm achieves comparable performance with the baseline WLAN algorithm (dashed red line), while if we focus only on the LTE infrastructure, the proposed algorithm requires significantly reduced PoA transmit power compared to the baseline LTE algorithm as well.

Figure 14: HO/VHO/NS probability versus the WLANblock deployment density

Fig. 14 illustrates the summation of the HO probability in the LTE network, the VHO probability between the LTE – WLAN systems, and the number of network selection events in the WLAN systems, for all algorithms and varying WLANblock deployment density. As expected, until the LTE system reaches its maximum capacity ($\sim d_W = 0.6$) the baseline LTE algorithm results in significantly lower HO/VHO/NS probability compared to both the proposed and the WLAN system, owing to the longer transmit – receive range between the MMT and the PoA. However, upon this threshold the number of VHO and NS events increases rapidly for the baseline LTE algorithm which ultimately reaches that of the other two competing schemes ($d_W = 0.9$). On the other hand, Fig. 14 demonstrates that the proposed and the baseline WLAN VHO algorithms show similar performance in terms of HO/VHO/NS probability. As a consequence, even though the deployment of the proposed algorithm results in multiple benefits for the MMT and the integrated LTE – WLAN system, it simultaneously results in similar HO/VHO/NS probability performance with the widely adopted approach to prioritize WLAN over LTE access (baseline WLAN algorithm).

Figure 15: Signaling Rate versus the WLANblock deployment density

Fig. 15 concludes our system-level simulation analysis by depicting the signaling rate, i.e., number of signals in the system per second, passing through the LTE and the WLAN systems as well as the ANDSF module for the VHO algorithms under scope. Note that the ANDSF signaling only applies to the proposed algorithm, which uses the concept of inter-system mobility policy to attain backwards compatibility with the LTE and WLAN systems. As expected, the baseline LTE algorithm results in the highest signaling rate among the LTE system as it avoids the utilization of the WLAN infrastructure. On the other hand, the LTE network signaling requirements for the baseline WLAN algorithm reduces rapidly and is practically diminished provided that the vast majority of users in the system prioritize WLAN access. Interestingly, the deployment of the proposed algorithm significantly reduces the LTE network signaling compared to the baseline LTE algorithm, however, it also significantly increases the WLAN network signaling owing to its requirement for signal quality measurement exchange between the wireless stations and the MMT. Nevertheless, the required signaling load is increasing linearly for increasing WLANblock deployment density, allowing the system level engineer to anticipate for the signaling requirements for deploying the proposed algorithm.

5.3 Discussion

Summarizing the results for the performance of the proposed algorithm and the two baseline VHO algorithms, we can state the following:

- Compared to the prioritized LTE or WLAN base algorithms, the proposed algorithm is shown to balance the number of users between the two heterogeneous systems.
- Compared to the prioritized LTE or WLAN base algorithms, the proposed algorithm is shown to reduce the mean MMT power consumption by approximately 82% and 73%, respectively.

- The proposed algorithm reduces the mean MMT power consumption by up to 93% compared to the baseline LTE VHO algorithm and up to 82% compared to the baseline WLAN VHO algorithm.
- The reduced power consumption of the proposed algorithm originates from the facts that a) it takes into account for the actual power consumption per interface state for the various RATs, and b) it also significantly reduces the mean transmit power of the MMTs on the target PoAs.
- The positive impact of the reduced MMT transmit power attained by the proposed VHO algorithm, is also depicted in terms of mean received interference power at the PoA sites.
- The smart utilization of both the LTE and WLAN systems, both in terms of balancing the number of users in the two systems and in terms of lowering the interference at the PoA sites, enables the proposed VHO algorithm to attain a significantly increased mean uplink capacity for the MMTs as well, compared to both the baseline WLAN and the baseline LTE algorithms.
- If we focus on the WLAN infrastructure only, the proposed algorithm achieves comparable performance with the baseline WLAN algorithm, while if we focus only on the LTE infrastructure, the proposed algorithm requires significantly reduced PoA transmit power compared to the baseline LTE algorithm as well.
- The proposed and the baseline WLAN VHO algorithms show similar performance in terms of HO/VHO/NS probability.

The aforementioned gains of the proposed algorithm are attained at the cost of an increased yet linearly increasing ANDSF and WLAN signaling rate with respect to the WLAN deployment density in the network.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have proposed ARCHON: an ANDSF-assisted energy-efficient VHO decision algorithm for the heterogeneous IEEE 802.11-2012 /LTE-A network. ARCHON utilizes recent enhancements to the 3GPP and IEEE Standards, including the deployment of the ANDSF and the provision for enhanced radio measurement capabilities at the heterogeneous PoAs. System-level simulations have shown that even though the deployment of ARCHON asks for increased ANDSF and WLAN network signaling, it enables efficient load balancing between the heterogeneous RATs, reduced MMT energy consumption per bit and enhanced uplink capacity per user. Future plans include performance analysis and detailed specification of the required network signaling procedure.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research has been funded by the European Commission as part of the SMART-NRG project (FP7-PEOPLE-2013-IAPP Grant number 612294).

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